

SQANTI3 report

Unique Genes: 12231

Unique Isoforms: 49870

Gene Classification

Category	Genes, count
Annotated Genes	11789
Novel Genes	442

Transcript Classification

Category	Isoforms, count
FSM	38379
ISM	57
NIC	7883
NNC	2773
Genic Genomic	37
Antisense	193
Fusion	258
Intergenic	183
Genic Intron	107

Splice Junction Classification

Category	SJs, count	Percent
Known canonical	138212	96.92
Known Non-canonical	169	0.12
Novel canonical	4040	2.83
Novel Non-canonical	185	0.13

Gene Characterization

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Number of Isoforms per Gene

Known vs Novel Genes

Distribution of Mono- vs Multi-Exon Transcripts

Structural Categories by Transcript Length

All Transcript Lengths Distribution

Transcript Lengths Distribution by Structural Category

Mono- vs Multi- Exon Transcript Lengths Distribution

Structural Isoform Characterization

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across FSM

Isoform Distribution Across ISM

Isoform Distribution Across NNC

Isoform Distribution Across NIC

Isoform Distribution Across Genic Genomic

Isoform Distribution Across Antisense

Isoform Distribution Across Fusion

Isoform Distribution Across Intergenic

Isoform Distribution Across Genic Intron

Transcript Lengths by Structural Classification

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Transcript Lengths by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Structural Classification

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Exon Counts by Subcategory

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Categories

Isoform Distribution Across Structural Subcategories

Length Distribution of Matched Reference Transcripts

Applicable Only to FSM and ISM Categories

Exon Count Distribution of Matched Reference Transcripts

Applicable Only to FSM and ISM Categories

Splice Junction Characterization

Distribution of Splice Junctions by Structural Classification

Distribution of Transcripts by Splice Junctions

RT-Switching All Junctions

Unique Junctions RT-switching

Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for FSM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS)

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS)

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for ISM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Start Site for ISM

Negative values indicate downstream of annotated TSS

*Comparison With Annotated TSS and TTS
by Subcategories*

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 3'5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Alternative 5'End

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to annotated Transcription Termination Site (TTS) FSM Reference Match

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated termination site

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM 3' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM 3' Fragment

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Intron Retention

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

Distance to Annotated Transcription Termination Site for ISM Intron Retention

Negative values indicate upstream of annotated TTS

PolyA Distance Analysis

Frequency of PolyA Motifs

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Category	Count	polyA Detected	%
FSM	38379	22978	60
ISM	57	41	72
NIC	7883	5990	76
NNC	2773	1898	68
Genic Genomic	37	22	59
Antisense	193	93	48
Fusion	258	193	75
Intergenic	183	59	32
Genic Intron	107	37	35

Motif	Count	%
AATAAA	19908	63.6
ATTAAA	4783	15.3
AGTAAA	1046	3.3
TATAAA	912	2.9
AAGAAA	533	1.7
CATAAA	500	1.6
TTTAAA	489	1.6
AATACA	465	1.5
AAAAAG	449	1.4
GATAAA	438	1.4
AATATA	412	1.3
AATGAA	401	1.3
GGGGCT	285	0.9
ACTAAA	267	0.9
AAAACA	212	0.7
AATAGA	211	0.7

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3'End by FSM and ISM Subcategories

Distance of Detected PolyA Motif From 3' End by Non-FSM/ISM Subcategories

Number of polyA Motifs Detected

Subcategory	Count	polyA Detected	%
Alternative 3'end	7971	3780	47
Alternative 3'5'end	8	3	38
Alternative 5'end	7460	4269	57
Reference match	21978	14393	65
3' fragment	2	2	100
Internal fragment	1	0	0
5' fragment	1	0	0
Comb. of annot. junctions	5002	3862	77
Comb. of annot. splice sites	1134	857	76
Intron retention	2199	1601	73
Mono-exon by intron ret.	12	8	67
At least 1 annot. don./accept.	2468	1677	68
Mono-exon	1247	635	51
Multi-exon	387	224	58

Frequency of PolyA Motifs

Motif	Count	%
AATAAA	19908	63.6
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AGTAAA	1046	3.3
TATAAA	912	2.9
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GGGGCT	285	0.9
ACTAAA	267	0.9
AAAACA	212	0.7
AATAGA	211	0.7

Redundancy Analysis

Reference Transcript Redundancy

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Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only FSM with a polyA motif found

Reference Transcript Redundancy

Only ISM with a polyA motif found

Reference Transcript Redundancy

FSM+ISM with a polyA motif found

Intra-Priming Quality Check

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Possible Intra-Priming by Structural Category

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Mono- vs Multi-Exon Possible Intra-Priming

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Coding vs Non-Coding Possible Intra-Priming

Percent of genomic 'A's in downstream 20 bp

Features of Bad Quality

RT-switching

Non-Canonical Junctions

Nonsense-Mediated Decay by Structural Category

Quality Control Attributes Across Structural Categories

Features of Good Quality

Annotation Support

PolyA Support

All Canonical Junctions

Good Quality Control Attributes Across Structural Categories

